

Issues Agreed Upon In The Interpretation Between Mujahid And Qatada Al-Baqara Sura As A Model

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 14, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 01, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Issues , Mujahid and Qatada Interpretation , Al-Baqara sura</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4487405</p>	<p><i>The research talks about the explanatory issues agreed upon by Mujahid bin Jabr and Qatada Their efforts were clear and clear in the interpretation of the Allah Holy Quraan and they were a reference for the interpreters after them, and those who follow their interpretation of the verses of Allah have agreed on many issues in the interpretation, so the two reseochers have decided to extract the issues agreed upon in the interpretation in Surat Al-Baqara only because there are many issues in the Holy Quraan and that Extending Allah in our ages, we will complete this project, Allah Almighty willing, and we do not know anyone who has compiled these issues and this is what called us to go into this topic in the service of the Book of Allah Almighty. The nature of the research required that it include an introduction, two studies and a conclusion: The introduction mentioned the reason for choosing the topic and the research plan. The first topic: The definition of the two imams was Mujahid and Qatada - may Allah Almighty have mercy on them - The second topic: The issues agreed upon in the interpretation of Surat Al-Baqara.</i></p>

Introduction

Praise be to Allah, we praise Him, seek His help, seek forgiveness, and seek refuge in Allah from the evils of ourselves and from the bad deeds of our actions. Whoever guides Allah does not mislead him, and he who is misled is not guided by him, and I testify that there is no god but Allah alone who has no partner. With charity until the Day of Judgment .. and after.

Allah Almighty revealed the Noble Qur'an to Muhammad - may Allah a prayers and peace be upon him - and made it a conclusion for the heavenly books (إِنَّا نَحْنُ نَزَّلْنَا الذِّكْرَ وَإِنَّا لَهُ لَحَافِظُونَ)

Old and modern researchers focused on studying everything related to the Book of Allah Almighty and extracting its meanings and explaining its rulings and rulings, due to the high status and status of the rest of the sciences. That its wonders do not pass, so scholars have followed throughout the ages from the age of blogging until today to interpreting the Holy Qur'an and contemplating it and managing its verses.

During these stages, great scholars emerged in all the science and art of their superior ability, outstanding talent, and brilliant genius, as well as the strength of conservation, the Queen of Understanding, and the energy of attainment and assimilation in their great and great legacy, especially with regard to the interpretation of the Book of Allah Almighty.

Among these most distinguished scholars: Mujahid bin Jabr Al Makhzoumi and Qatadah bin Da'meh Al-Sadousi, their efforts were clear and clear in the interpretation of the Book of Allah Almighty and they were a reference for the interpreters after them, and those who follow their interpretation of the verses of Allah Almighty find them have agreed on many issues in the interpretation, so we decided to extract the agreed issues In the interpretation in Surat Al-Baqara only because there are so many issues in the Holy Qur'an, and if Allah extends our ages, we will complete this project, Allah Almighty wills, and we do not know anyone who has compiled these issues and this is what called us to go into this topic in the service of the Book of Allah Almighty.

The First Topic: The Definition of Mujahid and Qatada

The First Requirement: Hmam Mujahid

Mujahid bin Jabr, and it is said: Ibn Jabir and the first is more correct, Makki, Abu Al-Hajjaj al-Qurashi al-Makhzoumi, Mawli al-Sa'ib bin Abi al-Sa'ib al-Makhzoumi, and it is said: Mala his son Abdullah ibn al-Sa'ib, and it is said: Molly Qais ibn al-Sa'ib al-Makhzoumi.

His Birth and Uprising:

He was born in Mecca in the succession of the Commander of the Faithful, Omar Al-Khattab, may Allah be pleased with him, in the year 21 AH. And his birth in this period, which was the period of the companions' spread in the country, and by taking it from a group of them as it comes with Allah's rule, he is considered one of the subordinate class.ⁱⁱ

His scholars:

It was taken from Abdullah bin Abbas, may Allah be pleased with them, and he adhered to it, as he heard from Ali Ibn Abi Talib, Abi bin Kaab, Abdullah bin Omar, Saad bin Abi Waqqas, Aisha al-Saddiqa, Abu Hurairah, Abu Saeed Al-Khudri, Abdullah bin Amr and Jaber. Bin Abdullah, Rafi bin Khadij ... and others.
His disciples

A group readout, including Ibn Katheer Al-Dari, Abu Amr Amr Ibn Al-Ala, and Muhaisin. is a modern linguist interpreter, a researcher of news and antiquities, and his knowledge of this was reflected in his interpretation, which was famous from the early ages, and was adopted by many imams and transferred many quotations from him, and in their forefront: Sufyan al-Thawri.

His interpretation:

This interpretation was famous for what the Imams of Hadith and Tafsir had reported from the era of al-Bukhari to the era of al-Mufsar al-Tabari, until after them, and Imam al-Tabari - may Allah have mercy on him - in particular, relied on the interpretation of Mujahid through his narration related to its owner, so that we can extract most of the texts of Mujahid's interpretation from Interpretation of al-Tabari with several novels.

Mujahid's interpretation of the interpretations that were reported by their companions by the narrators, and Mujahid narrates what he dictates to his disciples from what he heard from the nation's ink Ibn Abbas and other companions, then he uses his opinion to interpret some words based on what he knows from linguistic meanings, and he uses his opinion to clarify some of the indications To carry it on a known bearing of truth and metaphor.

In this way, Mujahid is counted in his interpretation of this narrated from him among the first to combine the dictum in the interpretation with some opinion, interpretation, and reference to rhetorical meanings.

The sayings of scholars concerning it:

IMAM Mujahid from the ferspectives of Other Scholars:

The position of Imam Mujahid appears from the testimonies of the imams of his predecessors,

Ibn Saad said: "The trust of a jurist is a scholar, a lot of hadith .ⁱⁱⁱ"

Yahya bin Moeen said: "Trust^{iv}"

Abu Hatim Ibn Hibban said: "His jurist was a devout worshiper, andartfnl .^v"

Yahya Al-Qattan said: " .^{vi}" Generally oknowled allah by the whole nation

Qatada said: "Know who is left with the interpretation: Mujahid .^{vii}"

Al-Hafiz Ibn Katheer said: "One of the imams of the followers and the interpreters were among the friends of Ibn Abbas, and he was the most knowledgeable of the people of his time with the interpretation until it was said: No one wanted knowledge for Allah's sake except Mujahid and Peacock .^{viii}"

He Death

Abu Naim said: Mujahid died while he was prostrating, two and a hundred years A.H. .^{ix} According to Ibn urban: the year eight hundred, narrated by him: his son; Abdullah, and with him: the year seven hundred, narrated: Muhammad ibn Umar Waaqidi, son of Greg, said: Mujahid reached three and eighty years old, said Yahya Al-Qattan, and others: Matt Year Four hundred^x

The Second CLIM: Qatada bin Daamah Al-Sadousi

Abu al-Khattab Qatada bin Daamah bin Aziz bin Amr bin Rabia bin Amr bin Al-Harith Ibn Sadous, Al-Sadous Al-Basri Al-Kamma, was a follower and a great scholar^{xi}Yeni was the father of the speech. He was

outharadative source in Hadith .^{xii} Al-Dhahabi said about him: (Preserve the power of interpreters and speakers, Abu Al-Khattab Al-Sadousi, Al-Basri, Al-Dir, and Al-Akka.^{xiii}

His Scholars

AS Narrated from Abdullah bin Sargassum, and Anas bin Malik, and Abu parasite Kanani, and Said bin Musayyib, high dad high-Riahi, and Safwan bin Mehrez, and Abu Othman Nahdi, and Zaraqarah bin fuller, Nadr ibn Anas, and Ikrima sire Ibn Abbas and Abu Maleeh bin Osama , Al-Hasan Al-Basri, and Bakr ibn Abd Allah Al-Muzni, Abu Hassan al-Araj, Hilal ibn Yazid, and Ata'a ibn Abi al-Ram, Molest Almenkera, and preached bin Mahtvz, Bashir bin heel, Abu Sha'tha Jaber bin Zaid, and Jerry Ben Clip Alsosa, Habib Ben Salem - as wrote to him - and Hassan bin Bilal, Hamid bin Abdul Rahman bin Auf, and Khalid bin Arafth, and Khalas AH, and Khaithamh Ben Abd al-Rahman, and Salim ibn Abi al-Ja`d, and Shahr ibn Hushab, Abd al-Abdullah ibn Shaqqiq, Aqabah ibn Sahab, Sunm, and Sunr Ibn Asim al-Laithi, my father Majlis, and my father Ayoub al-Maraghi, and my father the Gemini quartet.

And acco rdig to the authority of Imran ibn Husayn, Safinah, Abu Huraira, and on the authority of Muslim ibn Yasar, Qaza` ibn Yahya, and Shabir.^{xiv}

His Students

AS Narrated by the imams of Islam: Ayoub Alschiyanj, Ibn Abi Arabism, and Muammar bin Rashid, and Ouzai, and calorimeter bin Kadam, Amr ibn al-Harith al-Masri, and the Division of bin Hajjaj, and Jarir bin Hazim, and Shiban grammar, and Hammam Ben Yahia, and Hammad ibn Salamah, and Aban Attar, and happy Bin Bashir, Salam Bin Abi Muti`a, Shehab Bin Khurash, Husam Bin Masak, Khalid Bin Dalej, Sa`id Bin Zub, Sa`id Bin Zub Maadan, and Musa bin Khalaf al-Ami, and increases the son of Ibrahim Al-Tastari, and the father of Awana al-Waddah, and the nations of others.^{xv}

Other of the scholars in Perspectives is the top professional in memorizing holy Quraan.

Ibn Sirin said: (Qatada keep the people).^{xvi}

Muammar said: (Qatada stayed with Saeed bin al-Musayyib three days, and on the third day he said to him: Go away, blind man, you have bled me).^{xvii}

Qatada said: (I never told a Hadith teller: promise me, and I never heard anything in my ears except my heart's awareness).^{xviii}

Ahmad ibn Hanbal said: (Qatada is a scholar in interpretation, and according to different scholars, he was described as jurisprudence and memorization, and he was exaggerated in his remembrance, and he said: Say: You find noone to progress him).^{xix}

Ibn Mu`in said: (He did not listen from Saeed bin Jabir, nor from Mujahid).^{xx}

Bakr bin Abdullah said: (Whoever is pleased to look at the most memorable of those we have realized, let him look at Qatada).^{xxi}

Ibn al-Musayyib said: (We fond haroji in Quraan memori zation then Qatada).^{xxii}

The death of Qatada: He died in The second Topic: The issues agreed upon in Surat Al-Baqara

Mujahid and Qatada - may Allah have mercy on them - agreed on the interpretation of many Quranic verses, and I will mention what they agreed upon in Surat Al-Baqara:

They agreed that the Clpped letters cut at the beginning of Surat Al-Baqara are among the names of the Qur'an

Mujahid, : " Alif -Lan - Mim" is one of the names of the Qur'an^{xxiii}.

Aocording Qatada in his saying: "Pain" he said: It is one of the names of the Qur'an^{xxiv}.

And they agreed that the thirteen verses at the beginning of the Al-Baqara are among the characteristics of the hypocrites

Aocording of Mujahid, he said: This verse is thirteen, in the name of the hypocrites^{xxv}.

According to Qatada in his saying: ^{xxvi} (وَمِنَ النَّاسِ مَنْ يَقُولُ آمَنَّا بِاللَّهِ وَالْيَوْمِ الْآخِرِ وَمَا هُمْ بِمُؤْمِنِينَ) Until he reached: ^{xxvii} (فَمَا رِبِحَتْ) He said: These Versas describe the hypocrites.

And they agreed that their seclusion into their demons, that is, to their polytheistic companions

According to Mujahid, He is glorified and exalted: {And when they deviate to their demons} He said: "Their hypocrites and disbelieving companions^{xxviii} and for And on the authority of Qatada in his saying: (And if they abandon their demons), he said: (The polytheists).

^{xxix}

From Mujahid, in his words, glory, and majesty: {In their tyranny they blind them}^{xxx} Meaning: In their delusion, it means: hesitate. He says: "Allah has increased them astray to Z. Their delusion, and their blindness to their uncle «^{xxxi}

On the authority of Qatada, (in their tyranny, they blind them), that is, in their misguidance they blind^{xxxii}.

From Mujahid in his saying^{xxxiii} {الَّذِينَ اسْتَرَوْا الصَّلَاةَ بِالْهَدْيِ} Says: {فَلَمَّا أَضَاءَتْ مَا حَوْلَهُ} [Al-Baqarah: 17] He said : "أَمَا إِضَاءَةُ النَّارِ: coming to to the faithful and to the guidance, and either go Norm: Vakabbalhm to coming to and to misguidance, lighting and lighting and so on Azlamh ideals "^{xxxiv}

According to Mujahid: the Saib, the rain. On the authority of Qatada: "Or as a lieutenant," he says: Rain^{xxxv}.

According to Mujahid, in his words of honor and dignity: {جَامِعُهُمْ فِي جَهَنَّمَ} say {وَاللَّهُ مُجِيبٌ بِالْكَافِرِينَ} ^{xxxvi}.

From Mujahid, in his saying {مَا أَشْبِهَهُ بِهِ} ، يَقُولُ: «مِنْ كُلِّ صِنْفٍ مَثَلٌ» say: {الَّذِي رُزِقْنَا مِنْ قَبْلُ} ^{xxxvii}

It was narrated on the authority of Ibn Abi Najeh, on the authority of Mujahid, in his saying {وَأَتُوا بِهِ مُتَشَابِهًا} : Purify menstruation, feces, urine, slugs, ^{xxxviii} say^{xxxix} {وَلَهُمْ فِيهَا أَرْوَاحٌ مُطَهَّرَةٌ} : «خِيَارٌ، أَيْضًا» وَفِي قَوْلِهِ: {وَلَهُمْ فِيهَا أَرْوَاحٌ مُطَهَّرَةٌ} hypothalamus, semen and father »^{xl}

On the authority of Qatada: "They have purified husbands in them", meaning that Allah is guilty and sinful.

He said: Allah cleansed them from all urine, feces, and filth, and from every sin.

Purified menstruation, pregnancy and harm^{xli}.

On the authority of Qatada: "Bring it the same," meaning that it is an option that is not wasted and that the fruits of the world are purified from them and wasted from them.^{xlii}

On the authority of Mujahid: "They brought a surah like him," he said: "like him" is like the Qur'an^{xliii}

On the authority of Qatada in his saying: "They brought a surah like him", he says: Surah is similar to this Qur'an^{xliv}

About Mujahid, in the verse saying: {إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَا يَسْتَحْيِي أَنْ يَضْرِبَ مَثَلًا مَا بَعُوضَةً} ^{xlv} ، Means: «Proverbs all, large and small, believers believe in them, and they know the truth from their Lord and guide them by Allah » {and led astray by only adulterers} says: «know transgressors and disbelieve in Him»^{xlvi}

On the authority of Qatada, he said: "Allah is not embarrassed to give an example of a mosquito or more." That is, Allah does not be embarrassed by the right to mention something of it less or more.^{xlvii}

For the Mujahid, he said^{xlviii} {وَعَلَّمَ آدَمَ الْأَسْمَاءَ كُلَّهَا} Means: «مَا خَلَقَ اللَّهُ كُلَّهُ» : «بِأَسْمَاءٍ} : {أَنْبِئُونِي بِأَسْمَاءِ هَؤُلَاءِ} ^{xlix} هَذِهِ الَّتِي حَدَّثْتُ بِهَا آدَمَ»

On the authority of Qatada in his saying: "Adam knew all the names." He said: He taught him the name of everything, this is a mountain, and this is a sea. This is such and this and this, for everything. Then he presented these things to the angels and said: Tell me the names of these if you are truthful^l

According to Mujahid: "Then Adam received from his Lord words" he said: "Our Lord wronged us ourselves and if you did not forgive us and have mercy on us" the verse^{li}

According to Qatada in his saying: "Then Adam received from his Lord words." He said: He is saying: (ربنا ظلمنا أنفسنا وإن لم تغفر لنا وترحمنا لنكونن من الخاسرين)^{lii}

، ^{liii} { وَأَمِنُوا بِمَا أَنْزَلْتُ } ، Means : «الْقُرْآنُ» { مُصَدِّقًا لِمَا مَعَكُمْ } ، Means : «الْإِنْجِيلُ»^{liv} ،

About Mujahid, in his saying:^{lv} { وَإِذْ آتَيْنَا مُوسَى الْكِتَابَ } He said: "It is the separation, in which there is a difference between truth and falsehood"^{lvi}

Mujahid said: "Moses commanded his people from the command of his Lord Almighty to kill each other with machetes, they did, Allah turned to them, Aaron said unto them: « burned, Vohrkoh »"^{lvii}

On the authority of Mujahid, in his words the honorable and the exalted: { الْمَنَّ وَالسَّلْوَى }^{lviii} قَالَ : " : Manna: gum and amniocentesis: a bird "^{lix}

Qatada said in his statement: ، (وَأَنْزَلْنَا عَلَيْكَ الْمَنَّ وَالسَّلْوَى) He says: Manna used to descend upon them like snow^{lx}
On the authority of Qatada, he said: Al-Salwa: A bird that the south wind on them^{lxi}

About Mujahid, in his saying:^{lxii} { وَقُولُوا حِطَّةً } He said: "Bab Hutta, the door of the house of the Bible up, ordered the people of Moses to enter the door prostrate and say: Hetta and Tati door to scaling down their heads when they said they worshiped: wheat"^{lxiii}

About Qatada and Al-Hassan: (ادخلوا الباب سجداً) They said, they entered it on a side other than the one they had ordered, so they entered it, crawling at their hips, and exchanged a statement other than what they were told, and they said a grain in a rite.^{lxiv}

On the authority of Ibn Abi Najeh, on the authority of Mujahid, he said: "Fum: bread "^{lxv}
Qatada and Al-Hassan: Foam is the love that people hide^{lxvi}.

(اهبطوا مصرأ) He said: Egypt is insistent. They claimed that they did not return to Egypt.^{lxvii}

According Qatada in his saying: (Descend Egypt), He said: I mean, an insistence from the storms.^{lxviii}

On the authority of Mujahid, in his words the honorable^{lxix} { وَالصَّابِئِينَ } : He said: "They are the people of the Magi and the Jews, no religion, Select province mountain over them, says: It was narrated from the earth, Verwah above them Kzlh Calcahabh, said: mountain phase in Syriac, frightening, they entered prostrate on the letter, their eyes to the mountain, a mountain which is manifested Have his Lord "^{lxx}

On the authority of Qatada, he said: (And the Sabeans) said: The Sabeans worship people of the angels, they reach the qiblah, and they read Al-Zabur^{lxxi}

According Mujahid saying: (كونوا قردة خاسئين) He said: Saghirin.^{lxxii}

About Qatada: ، (خاسئين) He said: Saghirin^{lxxiii}

On the authority of Mujahid: (No obligation), he said: No major.^{lxxiv}

On the authority of Qatada: Al-Fared.^{lxxv}

For Mujahid: Al-Bakr, Al-Saghira, and Qatada: (ولا بكر) Not a small one.^{lxxvi}

On the authority of Mujahid: (Awan), he said: "Al-Awan": the half spinster .^{lxxvii} On the authority of Qatada: "Al-Awan", we described half of that^{lxxviii}

Mujahid said, saying: "There is no humiliation that stirs the land and does not water the plowing." N Qatada: It is not rubbish that raises the ground and does not water the plowing^{lxxix}

From Mujahid, in his saying: " { يَتْلُونَهُ حَقَّ تِلَاوَتِهِ } [Al-Baqarah: 121] "He said «يَعْمَلُونَ بِهِ حَقَّ عَمَلِهِ»^{lxxx} :

About Qatada: ، (يتلونه حق تلاوته) He said: Be permissible and prohibited, and do what is in it.^{lxxxi}

For Mujahid: { صِبْغَةَ اللَّهِ } [The Cow: 138] He said «يُعْنِي فِطْرَةَ الْإِسْلَامِ الَّتِي فَطَرَ النَّاسَ عَلَيْهَا»^{lxxxii} :
On the authority of Qatada: "Allah's character." He said: Allah's religion.^{lxxxiii}

From Mujahid: “{We have made you a mediating nation.” [Al-Baqarah: 143] Which is “justice” {لِتَكُونُوا شُهَدَاءَ} [Al-Baqarah: 143] “All nations are responsibleThe Jews, the Christians, and the Magi.” Fellows said: My son, Abu ^{لِخَاصَّةِ} قَالَ عُبَيْدُ بْنُ عُمَيْرٍ: يَأْتِي النَّبِيُّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ يَوْمَ الْقِيَامَةِ بِسَلَامٍ مِنْ رَبِّهِ، وَهُوَ فِي يَدَيْهِ كِتَابٌ فِيهِ أَسْمَاءُ كُلِّ نَفْسٍ مِنْكُمْ، فَتُحْشَرُ بِهَا يَوْمَ الْقِيَامَةِ. He and peace be upon him on the Day of Resurrection with his permission, no one with him, so the nation of Muhammad will be attested to by Allah, peace, and blessings of Allah be upon him^{lxxxiv}

On the authority of Qatada, he said: “A nation in the middle.” He said.^{lxxxv}

Mujahid: “{albeit a large [Baqarah: 143], means:« what they ordered by the conversion of a kiss from Jerusalem to the Kaaba, and when he turned to the Kaaba men about the place of women, men and women everywhere^{lxxxvi}»

On the authority of Qatada in his saying: “It is great except for those who guided God.” He said, Kabira, when the qiblah was transferred to the Sacred Mosque, so it was great except for those who guided God.^{lxxxvii}

About Mujahid, in his saying: {إِنَّ الَّذِينَ يَكْتُمُونَ مَا أَنْزَلْنَا مِنَ الْبَيِّنَاتِ وَالْهُدَى} [Al-Baqarah: 159] He said: They are the people of the book.^{lxxxviii}

On the authority of Qatada: “Those who conceal what we have revealed from evidence and guidance after what we have shown to people in the book.” Those people of the book concealed Islam, which is the religion of Allah.^{lxxxix}

From Mujahid: “{And the reasons were broken off” [Al-Baqarah: 166], meaning: “Affection”^{xc} ‘ On the authority of Qatada: “The reasons were interrupted by them”, the reasons for regret on the Day of Resurrection, and the reasons for the continuation that was between them in the world they communicate with and love with them, so they became a hostility on the Day of Resurrection, then on the Day of Resurrection, you will atone for each other, curse each other, and disavow one another^{xc1}

On the authority of Qatada in his saying: “Whoever is afraid of a man who commits scourge or a sin”, he said: He is the man who is commanded to be dishonored in his will, and the guardian returns it to truth and justice.^{xcii}

From Mujahid, in his saying: “{Al-Raft”} [Al-Baqarah: 187], he means: “Al-Jamma” from Qatada in his saying: “It is permissible for you on the night of fasting to be exalted to your wives.” He said: People before this verse had fallen asleep one night It is permissible for him to eat food and drink or for his wife to come to the next night, and some Muslims have fallen into it..^{xciii}

From Mujahideen: “{And show it to the rulers} [Al-Baqarah: 188]” He says: “Do not quarrel while you are unjust.”^{xciv} وَلَا تَأْكُلُوا عَنْ قِتَادَةِ قَوْلِهِ: "وَأَنْتَ أَعْلَمُ بِمَا فِي قُلُوبِهِمْ" Your wealth is between you in vain, and you refer it to the rulers. "And it was said: Whoever walks with his opponent when he is unjust, then he is a sinner until he returns to the truth. Know, O son of Adam, that the judge's ruling is not lawful for you and you are not entitled to falsehood, but the judge decides about what he sees and witnesses testify. And the judge is a human being who makes mistakes and wrongs, and know that whoever has been judged for falsehood, his opponent has not invalidated until God brings them together on the Day of Resurrection, and he will eliminate the nullified person for the right, with the best of what was decreed for the one who defeated the right in the world.^{xcv}

For Mujahid: {وَالْفِتْنَةُ أَشَدُّ مِنَ الْقَتْلِ} [Al-Baqarah: 191], he said: “The reversion of the believer to idol says more than he is rightly killed.” Qatada said: “And the temptation is more than the killing.” He says: Polytheism is more than killing.^{xcvi}

From Mujahid: “{And do not throw your hands into lethality” [Al-Baqarah: 195] He says, “The expense does not prevent you from the right of the fearfulness of Allah.”^{xcvii} On the authority of Qatada saying: "And spend for the sake of Allah and for Throw your hands into the wickedness. "He said: Qatada used to say that Al-Hassan had brought it up: they traveled and conquered and did not spend from their money, or he said: They do not spend on it, so Allah commanded them to spend in their sins for the sake of Allah..^{xcviii}

From Mujahid in his saying: “Hajj is months months of information.” [Al-Baqarah: 197] “It is a shawl with a base and ten days of that argumentOn the authority of Qatada, he said: “Hajj is the most famous information.” The most famous pilgrimage: Shawwal, Dhu al-Qi'dah, Dhu al-Hijjah, and he may have said: And the tenth of Dhu al-Hijjah.^{xcix}

According to Qatada saying: "It is not necessary for you to seek success in favor of your Lord." This neighborhood of the Arabs was not subject to a fraction of a misguided night of the night, and they called it "the night of the chest", and they did not seek trade or sale in it. So God Almighty granted all of this to the believers To shine their needs and seek the grace of their Lord.^c

From Mujahid, in his saying {لَيْسَ عَلَيْكُمْ جُنَاحٌ أَنْ تَبْتَغُوا فَضْلًا مِنْ رَبِّكُمْ} [Al-Baqarah: 198] said, "Trade in the season."^{ci}
From Mujahid: {ادْخُلُوا فِي السَّلَامِ كَافَّةً} [Al-Baqarah: 208], meaning: "In Islam all of us." On the authority of Qatada, he said: "Get in the peace." He said: Enter in Islam..^{ci}

From Mujahid {يَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ الْخَمْرِ وَالْمَيْسِرِ قُلْ فِيهِمَا إِثْمٌ كَبِيرٌ} [Al-Baqarah: 219] said: «This is the first thing Aept by wine» {and benefits for the people} [Al-Baqarah: 219] "What infest the time [p. 233] gambling, and gambling is gambling, but called the facilitator as saying: Oeerooa any Odzroa Kcolh: Put such and such "^{ciii}

According to Qatada, he said: gambling facilitator.^{civ}

From Mujahid {وَلَا تَجْعَلُوا اللَّهَ عُرْضَةً لِأَيْمَانِكُمْ} [Al-Baqarah: 224] He said: "command the righteous, the known, and the reformed."^{cv}

On the authority of Qatada saying: "And do not make Allah subject to your faith, that you may be righteous and fearful." He says: Do not arrogate to Allah, that one of you says that he did not pray as a womb, nor does he seek goodness, nor does he give charity from his wealth. Hey hey, may Allah bless you, for this Qur'an came only by leaving the matter of Satan, so do not obey him, and do not fulfill an order for him in anything of your vow or your faith..^{cvi}

From Mujahid {لَا يُؤَاخِذُكُمُ اللَّهُ بِاللَّغْوِ فِي أَيْمَانِكُمْ} [Al-Baqarah: 225] He said: It is that he swears by God and knows only that he is true to what he swore to him, then it is not like that. {وَلَكِنْ يُؤَاخِذُكُمْ بِمَا كَسَبْتُمْ قُلُوبَكُمْ} [Al-Baqarah: 225] He says: "By what your hearts have held upon it."^{cvi}

On the authority of Qatada, on the authority of Al-Hassan in his saying: "God does not take you with rhetoric in your faith." He said: He is the man who takes an oath over something, and he sees that it is..^{cvi}

From Mujahid {وَلَا يَجِلُّ} [Al-Baqarah: 228], meaning: "one menstrual period." {وَالْمُطَلَّقَاتُ يَتَرَبَّصْنَ بِأَنْفُسِهِنَّ ثَلَاثَةَ قُرُوءٍ} [Al-Baqarah: 228], meaning: "Pregnancy," he says: "The woman does not say: I am not pregnant, and she is pregnant, and she does not say that I am pregnant." {وَيُعَوْلُنَّهُنَّ أَحَقُّ بِرَدِّهِنَّ فِي ذَلِكَ} [Al-Baqarah: 228], means: "in the count"^{cix}

Qatada in his saying: "And divorced women lie in wait for themselves three readers." He says: Several divorced women carry three menstruation.^{cx}

From Mujahid {فَلَا تَعْضَلُوهُنَّ} [Al-Baqarah: 232] "She came down in a woman from an adornment that her husband divorced, so her brother made her reason that Bin Yasar would finish"^{cx}

On the authority of Qatada, he mentioned to us that a man divorced his wife at large, then he left her until her time had passed, then he approached him after marriage, and the woman is the sister of Ma'qal bin Yasar. Review it and have a pant of it! He refused to marry her. And he mentioned to us that when this verse was revealed to Allah, a prophet invited him and read it to him, so he left the diet and criticized the command of Allah.^{cxii}

According to Mujahid, in his words the honorable and the exalted: {and their preservation does not like him} He says: "He does not harm him, or his preservation abhors him"^{cxiii}

On the authority of Qatada in his saying: "And he does not protect them." He said: Nothing is too heavy for him.^{cxiv}

From Mujahid, {الَّذِي تَرَى إِلَى الْوَادِي خَاجٍ إِِبْرَاهِيمَ فِي رَبِّهِ} [Al-Baqarah: 258] He said, "It is Nimrud, the son of Canaan."^{cxv}

On the authority of Qatada: "Did you not see who Haj Ibrahim had in his Lord?" He said: We used to talk that he was a king called "a nurtured", the first king to be forced into the land, and he is the owner of the edifice in Babylon..^{cxvi}

From Mujahid [{فَصَرْهُنَّ إِلَيْكَ} Al-Baqarah: 260] He said: He said: "Take off their feathers and their flesh and tear them apart." On the authority of Qatada: (So behold them to you) The command of the Prophet of Allah, peace be upon him, to take four birds and slaughter them, then mix them with their meat..^{cxvii}

From Mujahid In his saying: “wisdom is paid to whomever He wills.” [Al-Baqarah: 269] He said: “The Qur’an will cause His injury to whom He will.”^{cxviii}

From Mujahid {لِلْفُقَرَاءِ الَّذِينَ أُحْصِرُوا فِي سَبِيلِ اللَّهِ} [Al-Baqarah: 273], means: «Quraish immigrants in the city with the Prophet peace be upon him», he said: «ordered them to give charity», and saying: {} you know Besimahm [Al-Baqarah: 273], means: «From Altkhca»^{cxix}

On the authority of Qatada in his saying: “Those who are trapped in the path of Allah,” he said: They surrounded themselves in the path of Allah’s conquest.

Mujahid, saying: {who devour usury will not only as of the person was beaten by the devil touch} [Al-Baqarah: 275], he said, means «the Day of Resurrection, what to eat usury in the world»^{cxx}

Qatada said: And that is the sign of the people of usury on the Day of Resurrection^{cxxi}

Conclusion

Praise be to Allah, who helped us to complete this research, and we have reached several results, the most important of which are:

- 1) Mujahid and Qatada are considered among the most important sources of the commentators, and Imam al-Tabari and others were taken from them.
- 2) Mujahid and Qatada agreed on many issues in Surat Al-Baqara and other suras
- 3) The interpretation of Mujahid and Qatada was characterized by short and clear

Reference

- Margins, sources, and references
The Holy Quran

ⁱSurah Al-Hijr: 9

ⁱⁱLooking: Wound and modification by Ibn Abi Hatim: 8/319

ⁱⁱⁱThe same source

^{iv}The Great Classes Bin Saad: 6/20 I Scientific Surah

^vLooking: Wound and modification by Ibn Abi Hatim: 8/319

^{vi}The golden balance of moderation: 3/440

^{vii} Layers of hadith scholars: Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Ahmed bin Abdul Hadi: 1/163 Refining the discipline of Ibn Hajar: 10/43

^{viii}The beginning and the end of Ibn Katheer: 9/250

^{ix} The major classes of Ibn Saad: 5/467

^xLooking: The course of the nobles' flags: 4/456

^{xi}Senate deaths: 4/85

^{xii}The major classes, by Ibn Saad: 7/171

^{xiii}The course of the nobles' flags: 5/270

^{xiv}Layers of hadith scholars, Ibn Abd al-Hadi al-Dimashqi: 1/169

^{xv}The layers of Ibn Saad: 7/230

^{xvi}The course of the nobles' flags: 5/277

^{xvii}Wound and Modification: 7/133

^{xviii}Fine tune:

^{xix} Wound and Modification: 7/134

^{xx} The course of the nobles' flags: 5/277

^{xxi}Wound and Modification: 7/133

^{xxii}The same source

^{xxiii}Tafseer Al-Tabari: 1/205

^{xxiv}Tafseer Al-Tabari: 1/205

^{xxv} Interpretation of al-Tabari: 1/269

^{xxvi} Al-Baqara: 8

^{xxvii} Interpretation of al-Tabari: 1/269

^{xxviii} The interpretation of Mujahid: 1/196

^{xxix} Tafseer Al-Tabari: 1/397

^{xxx} Al-Baqara: 15

^{xxxi} The interpretation of Mujahid: 1/196

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- xxxii Tafseer Al-Tabari: 1/309
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